

A Bay/Estuary Model to Simulate Hydrodynamics and Water Quality Transport: Part 2: Water Quality

Jing Yu¹, Gour-Tsyh Yeh¹, Tien-Shuenn Wu², and Gordon Hu³

¹Dept of Civil and Environ. Eng., Univ. of Central Florida, Orlando, FL 32816, USA

²Florida Dept of Environmental Protection, Tallahassee, FL 32399, USA

³South Florida Water Management District, West Palm Beach, FL 33406, USA

ABSTRACT

This paper presents the development of a numerical water quality model using a general paradigm of reaction-based approaches. In a reaction-based approach, all conceptualized biogeochemical processes are transformed into a reaction network. Through the decomposition of species governing equations via Gauss-Jordan column reduction of the reaction network, (1) redundant fast reactions and irrelevant kinetic reactions are removed from the system, which alleviates the problem of unnecessary and erroneous formulation and parameterization of these reactions, and (2) fast reactions and slow reactions are decoupled, which enables robust numerical integrations. The system of M species transport equations is transformed to M reaction-extent transport equations, which is then approximated with three subsets: N_E algebraic equations, N_{KI} kinetic-variables transport equations, and N_C component transport equations. As a result, the model alleviates the needs of using simple partitions for fast reactions. With the diagonalization strategy, it makes the inclusion of arbitrary number of fast and kinetic reactions relatively easy, and, more importantly, it enables the formulation and parameterization of kinetic reactions one by one. To demonstrate the general paradigm, we recast QAUL2E in the mode of a reaction network. We then applied the model to the Loxahatchee estuary to study its response to a hypothetical biogeochemical loading from its surrounding drainage. Preliminary results indicated that the model properly simulate four interacting biogeochemical processes: algae kinetics, nitrogen cycle, phosphorus cycle, and Dissolved Oxygen Balance.

1. INTRODUCTION

Many of most widely used water quality models, e.g., QUAL2E (Brown and Barnwell, 1987), WASP (Di Toro et al., 1983; Connolly and Windfied, 1984; Ambrose et al., 1988, 1993; Wool et al.), and CE-QUAL-ICM (Cercio and Cole, 1995), are physics-based and mechanistically similar. The major differences among them are the number of water quality parameters included and the number of biogeochemical processes considered. Obviously, there is a need to develop a model that would allow the inclusion of any number of water quality parameters and enable the consideration of any number of biogeochemical processes. This paper presents the development of a Bay/Estuary Model to Simulate Hydrodynamics and Thermal, Salinity, Sediment and Water quality Transport in 3-Dimensions Version 2.0 (BEST3D 2.0)

In BEST3D 2.0, sediments are categorized based on their physical and chemical properties (Zhang, 2005). For each kind of sediment, the model includes mobile suspended sediment particles scattered in the water column and immobile bed sediment particles accumulated in

the bottom. The biogeochemical species are classified according to the six phases in which they exist and the three forms they appear. The six phases are suspended sediment, bed sediment, aqueous water, pore water, suspension precipitate, and bed precipitate phases. The three forms are dissolved chemicals, precipitates, and particulate chemicals sorbed onto sediments. Biogeochemical species in the water column are considered to be mobile. Biogeochemical species in the bottom are considered to be immobile. In the model, the biogeochemical reactions are divided into two classes based on the comparison between reaction rate and transport time scale: fast/equilibrium reaction and slow/kinetic reactions. Through decomposition of reaction network via Gauss-Jordan column reduction, BEST3D 2.0 is designed to include as many types of reactions as possible, choose reaction extents instead of biogeochemical species as primary dependent variables, and simplify the reaction terms in transport equations.

2. MATHEMATICAL MODEL

The balance equation for bed sediments is simply the statement that the rate of mass change is due to erosion/deposition as (Yeh et al., 2005):

$$\frac{\partial B \bar{M}_n}{\partial t} = D_n - R_n, n \in [1, N_s] \quad \text{and} \quad \frac{\partial B}{\partial t} = \sum_{n=1}^{N_s} \frac{D_n - R_n}{\rho_n} \quad (1)$$

where B is the bed thickness [L]; \bar{M}_n is the n -th bed sediment concentration averaged over the bed thickness in the unit of mass per unit bed volume [M/L³]; t is the time [T]; D_n is the deposition rate of the n -th sediment in the unit of mass per unit bed area per unit time [M/L²/T]; R_n is the erosion rate of the n -th sediment in the unit of mass per unit bed area per unit time [M/L²/T]; N_s is the number of sediment size-fractions; and ρ_n is the density of the n -th size-fraction [M/L³].

The transport equation of suspended sediment can be derived based on the conservation law of material mass as:

$$\frac{\partial S_n}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\mathbf{V} S_n) + \frac{\partial W_{sn} S_n}{\partial z} - \nabla \cdot (\mathbf{K} \cdot \nabla S_n) = M_n^{as}, \quad n \in [1, N_s] \quad (2)$$

where S_n is the concentration of the n -th suspended sediment in the unit of mass per unit surface-water volume [M/L³]; t is the time [T]; \mathbf{V} is the flow velocity [L/T]; W_{sn} is the settling velocity of the n -th sediment fraction [L/T]; \mathbf{K} is the dispersion coefficient tensor [L²/T]; M_n^{as} is the artificial source of the n -th suspended sediment [M/L³/T].

The balance equation for immobile species is simply the statement that the rate of mass change is due to biogeochemical reaction and the interfacial exchange from water column to the bed layer due to diffusion (for dissolved species), settling (for precipitate species), or deposition and erosion (for particulate species) as:

$$\frac{\partial (B \rho_i C_i)}{\partial t} - F_{i:C \rightarrow B} = B r_{Ci} \Big|_N \quad (3)$$

where B is the bed depth [L]; $\rho_i = \rho_{bw} \theta_b$ for pore-water dissolved species and precipitated species in pore-water, ρ_{bw} is the density of bed pore-water [M/L³], θ_b is the porosity of the bed sediment [L³/L³]; $\rho_i = \bar{M}_n$ for particulate species sorbed onto the n -th bed sediment; C_i is the concentration of the i -th species in the unit of chemical mass per phase mass [M/M]; t is the time [T]; $F_{i:C \rightarrow B}$ is exchange rate of the i -th species from water column to the bed layer

due to diffusion, settling, or deposition/erosion in the unit of chemical mass per unit bed area per unit time $[M/t/L^2]$; and $r_{C_i}|_N$ is the production rate of the i -th species due to all N reactions in the unit of chemical mass per bed volume per unit time $[M/L^3/t]$.

The transport equation of mobile species can be derived based on the conservation law of material mass stating that the rate of mass change is due to both advective-dispersive transport and biogeochemical reactions as:

$$\frac{\partial(\rho_i C_i)}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\mathbf{V} \rho_i C_i) + \frac{\partial W_{si} \rho_i C_i}{\partial z} - \nabla \cdot [\mathbf{D} \cdot \nabla(\rho_i C_i)] - M_{C_i}^{as} = r_{C_i}|_N \quad (4)$$

where $\rho_i = \rho_w$ for dissolved species and precipitated species, ρ_w is the density of surface-water $[M/L^3]$; $\rho_i = S_n$ for the n -th particulate species; C_i is the concentration of the i -th species in the unit of chemical mass per phase mass $[M/M]$; t is the time $[T]$; \mathbf{V} is the fluid velocity $[L/t]$; W_{si} is the settling velocity of the i -th species $[L/t]$, for a dissolved species $W_{si} = 0$; \mathbf{D} is the dispersion coefficient tensor $[L^2/t]$; $M_{C_i}^{as}$ is the artificial source of the i -th species in chemical mass per unit volume of column water $[M/L^3]$; and $r_{C_i}|_N$ is the production rate of C_i due to all N reactions in the unit of chemical mass per surface-water volume per time $[M/L^3/t]$.

In a reaction-based formulation, $r_{C_i}|_N$ in Eq. (3) or (4) is given by the summation of rates of all reactions in which the i -th water quality participates,

$$r_{C_i}|_N = \frac{dC_i}{dt} \Big|_{reaction} = \sum_{k \in N} (v_{ik} - \mu_{ik}) R_k, \quad i \in M \quad (5)$$

where v_{ik} is the reaction stoichiometry of the i -th species in the k -th reaction associated with the products, μ_{ik} is the reaction stoichiometry of the i -th species in the k -th reaction associated with the reactants, and R_k is the rate of the k -th reaction $[M/L^3]$.

Substitution of Eq. (5) into Eq. (4) yields

$$\frac{\partial(\rho_i C_i)}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\mathbf{V} \rho_i C_i) + \frac{\partial W_{si} \rho_i C_i}{\partial z} - \nabla \cdot [\mathbf{D} \cdot \nabla(\rho_i C_i)] - M_{C_i}^{as} = \sum_{k \in N} (v_{ik} - \mu_{ik}) R_k, \quad i \in M \quad (6)$$

Performing matrix decomposition of the reaction matrix on Eq. (6), we have

$$\frac{\partial(E_i)}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\mathbf{V} E_i) + \frac{\partial W_{sp} E_i^p}{\partial z} + \sum_{n \in N_s} \frac{\partial W_{sn} E_i^{sn}}{\partial z} - \nabla \cdot [\mathbf{D} \cdot \nabla(E_i)] - M_{E_i}^{as} = D_{kk} R_k + \sum_{j \in N_{KL(k)}} D_{ij} R_j, \quad (7)$$

where $E_i = \sum_{j \in M} a_{ij}(\rho_j C_j)$, $E_i = \sum_{j \in M_p} a_{ij}(\rho_j C_j)$, $E_i = \sum_{j \in M_{Sn}} a_{ij}(\rho_j C_j)$, $i \in M$ and $k \in N$

where E_i is the i -th reaction extent which is the linear combination of $\rho_j C_j$ resulted from the matrix decomposition of a unit matrix; E_i^p is the portion of E_i , which contains the linear combination of only precipitated species; E_i^{sn} is the portion of E_i , which contains the linear combination of only particulate species; $M_{E_i}^{as}$ is the artificial source of E_i , which is the linear combination of $M_{C_i}^{as}$; D_{ij} is the i -th row and j -th column of the Gauss-Jordan reduced reaction matrix; $N_{KL(k)}$ is the set of kinetic reactions that are linearly dependent on the k -th linearly independent reaction; a_{ij} is the decomposed unit matrix; M_p is the number of precipitated species; M_{Sn} is the number of species adsorbed to sediment fraction n ; and D_{kk} is the k -th diagonal entry of the decomposed reaction matrix.

The concentration of all bed sediments, suspended sediments, and chemical species must be given initially for transient simulations. Initial concentration is obtained by field measurement or by solving a steady-state version of the governing equations. No boundary condition is needed for bed sediments and immobile species. Four types of boundary conditions for suspended sediments and mobile species are taken into account. These boundary conditions include Dirichlet boundary, Variable boundary, Cauchy boundary, Neumann boundary.

3. NUMERICAL APPROXIMATIONS

One of the most critical issues in physics-based water quality modeling is the use of appropriate numerical methods to approximate the governing equations. For research applications, the model needs to use accurate and robust methods. For practical applications, it needs to employ efficient and robust methods. Considering that there can be wide ranges of transport conditions for real-world problems, we provide many numerical options in the model.

For transport simulations (including sediment and water quality), two options are provided to discretize the governing sediment and biogeochemical transport equations: hybrid Lagrangian-Eulerian finite element methods or conventional finite element methods. Three schemes are employed to handle the coupling between the hydrologic transport and biogeochemical reactions: fully implicit sequential iteration approach, operator splitting, and mixed predictor-corrector and operator-splitting. The Newton-Raphson method was used to solve the set of algebraic equations and ordinary equations describing the evolution of all biogeochemical species.

4. APPLICATION

4.1 Reaction Paradigm of QUAL2E

The eutrophication model in QUAL2E can be recast in the mode of reaction network (Table 1). There are a total of 9 reagents involved in 16 kinetic reactions in QAUL2E (Table 1). These 16 reactions can be classified into four groups: Algal kinetics (Reaction 1~4), Nitrogen cycle (Reaction 5~9), Phosphorus cycle (Reaction 10~12), and Dissolved Oxygen Balance (Reaction 13~16). In the original reports, there are 9 water qualities (reagents) simulated in QUAL2E. In the context of reaction network, there should be 19 constituents involved in QUAL2E.

In QUAL2E, all rate equations depend on only the first 9 constituents (DO, BOD, Chla, NH₄, ON, NO₂, NO₃, OP, and OPO₄), thus, the other 10 constituents (DO_(b), BOD_(b), Chla_(b), NH_{4(b)}, ON_(b), OP_(b), OPO_{4(b)}, CO₂, H₂O, and O_{2(g)}) can be decoupled from the first 9 in any simulation. Had evidence indicated that the rate formulation of the 16 kinetic reactions also depends on the other 10 constituents in a system, then all 19 constituents should have been modeled simultaneously. Therefore, when QUAL2E is applied to any system, the first order of business is to check if the rate formulation for the 16 kinetic reactions is valid. If it does, then one can consider other issues involved in applying the model to his/her system. If any of the 16 rate equations is invalid, then one should not apply the model to his/her system.

TABLE 1. QUAL2E Reaction Network

No.	Mechanism	Reaction	Rate
1	Algae growth	$\alpha_1\text{NH}_4 + \alpha_2\text{OPO}_4 + \text{H}_2\text{O} + \text{CO}_{2(\text{g})} \rightarrow \alpha_0\text{Chla} + \alpha_3\text{DO} + (\alpha_4 - \alpha_3)\text{O}_{2(\text{g})}$	$R = \frac{\mu}{\alpha_0}\theta^{T-20}\text{Chla}$
2	Diatom growth related nitrate reduction	$\text{NO}_3 + 1.5\text{H}_2\text{O} \rightarrow \text{NH}_4 + (\alpha_5 + \alpha_6)\text{O}_{2(\text{g})}$	$R = (1-F)\alpha_1\frac{\mu}{\alpha_0}\theta^{T-20}\text{Chla}$
3	Algae respiration	$\alpha_0\text{Chla} + \alpha_4\text{DO} \rightarrow \alpha_1\text{ON} + \alpha_2\text{OP} + \text{H}_2\text{O} + \text{CO}_{2(\text{g})}$	$R = \frac{\rho}{\alpha_0}\theta^{T-20}\text{Chla}$
4	Algae settling	$\text{Chla} \rightarrow \text{Chla}_{(\text{b})}$	$R = \frac{\sigma_1}{d}\theta^{T-20}\text{Chla}$
5	Mineralization of organic nitrogen	$\text{ON} \rightarrow \text{NH}_4$	$R = \beta_3\theta^{T-20}\text{ON}$
6	Organic nitrogen settling	$\text{ON} \rightarrow \text{ON}_{(\text{b})}$	$R = \sigma_4\theta^{T-20}\text{ON}$
7	Biological oxidation of ammonia nitrogen	$\text{NH}_4 + \alpha_5\text{DO} \rightarrow \text{NO}_2 + 1.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$	$R = \beta_1\text{CORDO}\theta^{T-20}\text{NH}_4$
8	Benthos source to ammonia nitrogen	$\text{NH}_{4(\text{b})} \rightarrow \text{NH}_4$	$R = \sigma_3\theta^{T-20}/d$
9	Oxidation of nitrate nitrogen	$\text{NO}_2 + \alpha_6\text{DO} \rightarrow \text{NO}_3$	$R = \beta_2\text{CORDO}\theta^{T-20}\text{NO}_2$
10	Organic phosphorus decay	$\text{OP} \rightarrow \text{OPO}_4$	$R = \beta_4\theta^{T-20}\text{OP}$
11	Organic phosphorus settling	$\text{OP} \rightarrow \text{OP}_{(\text{b})}$	$R = \sigma_5\theta^{T-20}\text{OP}$
12	Benthos source to dissolved phosphorus	$\text{OPO}_{4(\text{b})} \rightarrow \text{OPO}_4$	$R = \sigma_2\theta^{T-20}/d$
13	Deoxygenating of BOD	$\text{DO} + \text{BOD} \rightarrow \text{CO}_{2(\text{g})} + \text{H}_2\text{O}$	$R = K_1\theta^{T-20}\text{BOD}$
14	BOD settling	$\text{BOD} \rightarrow \text{BOD}_{(\text{b})}$	$R = K_3\theta^{T-20}\text{BOD}$
15	Re-aeration	$\text{O}_{2(\text{g})} \rightarrow \text{DO}$	$R = K_2\theta^{T-20}(\text{DO}^* - \text{DO})$
16	Sediment oxygen demand	$\text{DO} \rightarrow \text{DO}_{(\text{b})}$	$R = K_4\theta^{T-20}/d$

4.2 A Hypothetical Application to Loxahatchee Estuary

To demonstrate the general paradigm, we apply QAUL2E to the Loxahatchee estuary to study its response to a hypothetical biogeochemical loading (e.g., TMDL) from its surrounding drainage (Table 2). The Loxahatchee Estuary central embayment is at the confluence of three major tributaries: the Northwest Fork, the North Fork, and the Southwest Fork. This example demonstrates the capability of the model in simulating biogeochemical transport related to eutrophication kinetics. Several physical-chemical processes can affect the transport and interaction among the nutrients, algae, carbonaceous material, and dissolved oxygen in the aquatic environment. QUAL2E (Brown and Barnwell, Jr. 1987) simulates the transport and transformation reactions of up to 15 constituents. Here we focus on nine interacting non-conservative biogeochemical constituents (Table 2) excluding temperature, coliforms, one non-reacting non-conservative constituent, and three conservative constituents.

The computational domain covers a part of the Atlantic Ocean, the North Intracoastal Waterway, the South Intracoastal Waterway, the entire North Fork of the Loxahatchee River, the Southwest Fork up to Structure S46, and the Northwest Fork up to the Florida Turnpike (Figure 1). Water depth ranges from 0.9 m to 7.3 m. The maximum river width is about 1,018 m, and the minimum river width is about 4.6 m. The domain is discretized with 4,936 quadratic, triangular prism elements resulting in 30,664 nodes. The element size ranges from 1,067 m in Atlantic Ocean to 4.6 m near Kitching Creek. BEST3D Version 1.0 (Yeh et al.,

2005) was used to generate hydrodynamics including currents, tides, salinity, and temperature distributions.

TABLE 2. Hypothetical initial and boundary conditions for the Loxahatchee River simulations.

Species	Initial Concentration	Concentration in freshwater	Concentration in seawater	Units
O	0.50	5.00	0.50	Mg-O ₂ /Liter
BOD	0.08	0.80	0.08	Mg-O ₂ /Liter
Chl _a	2.00	20.00	2.00	μg-Chl _a /Liter
NH ₄	0.20	2.00	0.20	Mg-N/Liter
ON	0.10	1.00	0.10	Mg-N/Liter
NO ₂	0.01	0.10	0.01	Mg-N/Liter
NO ₃	0.10	1.00	0.10	Mg-N/Liter
OP	0.05	0.50	0.05	Mg-P/Liter
OPO ₄	0.01	0.10	0.01	Mg-P/Liter

FIGURE 1. Computational domain and finite element discretization.

The simulation results for algae as chlorophyll a (Chl_a), organic nitrogen (ON), biochemical oxygen demand (BOD), and dissolved oxygen (DO) at two different times are shown in Figures 2 through 5. The source of algae is its growth and the sink is its respiration. Figure 2 shows an increasing concentration with time, signaling that the source is greater than the sink.

The source of organic nitrogen in water column includes algae respiration. The sink includes the mineralization of its dissolved fraction and the settlement of its particular fraction. Figure 3 shows a decreasing concentration of organic nitrogen with time, signaling a greater sink than source.

There is no source for BOD. However, its sink includes oxidation of its dissolved fraction and the settlement of its particular fraction. Figure 4 shows a decreasing concentration of BOD with time.

The source of dissolved oxygen is the algae growth and re-aeration from the air. The sink includes algae respiration and oxidation of ammonia, nitrite, and BOD as well as the sediment oxidation demand. Figure 5 shows an increasing concentration of dissolved oxygen with time, signaling that the source is greater than the sink.

FIGURE 2. Distribution of Chl_a at t = 1h (left) and t = 96 h (right)

FIGURE 3. Distribution of organic nitrogen at t = 1h (left) and t = 96 h (right)

FIGURE 4. Distribution of BOD at t = 1h (left) and t = 96 h (right)

FIGURE 5. Distribution of dissolved oxygen at t = 1h (left) and t = 96 h (right)

5. SUMMARY

It is inflexible for most current widely used water quality models to handle any number of state variables and any number of reactions. This paper presents a generic paradigm that allows users to include any number of state variables with ease and the framework is applicable to receiving waters. The key of the paradigm is the reaction-based approach and the decomposition of reaction networks. The reaction-based approach allows one to include

any number of reactions, thus any number of state variables. The decomposition allows the formulation of rate equations one reaction at a time with a proper design of experimental systems. The paradigm will provide an easy way to achieve the objective of incorporating new findings. To demonstrate the general paradigm, we recast QAUL2E in the mode of a reaction network. We then applied the model the Loxahatchee estuary to study its response to a hypothetical biogeochemical loading from its surrounding drainage. Preliminary results indicated that the model properly simulate four interacting biogeochemical processes: algae kinetics, nitrogen cycle, phosphorus cycle, and Dissolved Oxygen Balance.

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